

Physical fitness as one of the directions of the historical development of physical culture

Vasyl Sutula¹
Larisa Lutsenko²
Andrey Zhadan¹
Anastasiia Sutula³

¹Kharkiv State Academy of Physical Culture, Kharkiv, Ukraine
²Law University named after Yaroslav the Wise, Kharkiv, Ukraine
³National Pharmaceutical University, Kharkiv, Ukraine

Purpose: to reveal the cultural and historical origins of the concept of "physical fitness".

Material & Methods: an analysis of specialized literature covering various aspects of the development of the field of human activity associated with the use of physical exercises.

Results: at the turn of the 20th century, the term "physical culture" was used as a generalising name for the three areas of people's activities related to the use of physical exercises: activities aimed at bringing the body in line (physical fitness) activities aimed at developing physical strength and body build (bodybuilding) activities aimed at improving through the use of physical exercises (therapeutic physical culture).

Conclusion: in terms of the theory of physical culture of physical fitness is seen as a particular socio-cultural phenomenon, which is a historically conditioned human activity involving the use of physical exercise at their leisure, and individual and socially significant results of such activities.

Keywords: physical culture, physical fitness, theory, law of "interrelation of needs and activities".

Introduction

A necessary condition for the successful development of the theory of physical culture [2; 5] as a theory revealing the driving forces, social mechanisms and objective laws of the historical development of people's activities related to the use of physical exercises is the establishment of the sociocultural nature of the process of changing terms and concepts that were formed as a result of cognitive process. In previous reports, generalizing (consensus) definitions of the concepts "physical culture" [3] and "sport" are presented [4]. Continuing the analysis begun, let us pay attention to the cultural and historical origins of the concept of "physical fitness". The need for such an analysis stems from the fact that in a broad social and scientific practice there is no correct substantiation of this concept. For example, G. Glassman [7] notes that a significant part of fitness programs do not give a clear definition of the concept of "fitness". According to the expert, the Encyclopedic Dictionary, in which the concept of "fitness" is interpreted as the ability to transfer genes and be healthy, does not help either. He also draws attention to the fact that NSCA, a respected publisher in the field of exercise physiology, in his authoritative publication *Essentials of Strength Training and Conditioning* did not even attempt to define this concept. E. Corre [8] notes in his research that E. Desbonnet and B. Macfadden are pioneers in the health industry, after which society enters the age of confusion, in the age of the fitness business. The examples given indicate that the problem of the correct definition of the concept of "physical fitness" now requires a more detailed analysis.

Purpose of the study: to reveal the cultural and historical sources of the concept of "physical fitness".

Material and Methods of the research

Research methods consist in the analysis of the special literature, which highlights the historical aspects of the development of various forms of social manifestation of physical culture, as well as the use of a systematic and historiographical approach to the analysis of this problem.

Results of the research

The correct understanding of the concept of "physical fitness" is possible only within the framework of the theory of physical culture, namely, through the prism of the general definition of the concept of "physical culture". In the previous message it was shown that physical culture is a historically conditioned activity of people associated with the use of physical exercises, and its individual and socially significant results [3]. That is, in this definition, attention is drawn to the two components of the concept of "physical culture" – an activity and resultant. Analyzing the problem of using the terms "physical culture" and "physical fitness" in the English language, one should pay attention to the fact that the activity of people using physical exercises has not only the effect of forming their corporeality (this direction was called bodybuilding [6]), such activity also significantly affects the general level of physical well-being of a person, on his suitability for fulfilling life's important tasks. J. Sifferman [9] draws attention to this feature, noting that physical culture is more than just bodybuilding. According to a specialist, it represents a certain philosophy, mode or lifestyle, and is aimed at maximizing the physical, mental, spiritual and social development of a person. So, this activity of people with the use of physical exercises is aimed at improving their ability to respond adequately to the various challenges that arise

in the process of life activity. Using the generalized definition of the concept of "physical culture" [3], we can conclude that, based on the resultant effect of people's activities using physical exercises, which formed their physical fitness, physical conformity, this is the direction of development of physical culture at the turn of the 20th century in the English-speaking practice called "physical fitness". He began to develop intensively, starting at about the beginning of the 20th century. The frequency of the use of the term "physical fitness" in the 1930s equated with the frequency of the use of the term "physical culture", and in the future it significantly outstripped it, which is an objective consequence of the intense development of that period of the fitness industry (Figure).

Figure. Dynamics of use of the terms "physical culture", "physical fitness" from 1800 to 2008 (English) (obtained using the search engine "Google Books Ngram Viewer") (access mode: <https://books.google.com/ngrams>)

According to historical materials, B. McFadden, the pioneer of the health industry [8], as a successful businessman, was aware of the importance of this trend in the use of physical exercise and sought to consolidate his rights to it. This hypothesis is confirmed by the information contained in the "Annotated Bibliography of English Literature Series in the Field of Physical Culture" (for the period from 1829 to 1990 inclusive), prepared by the Center for Physical Culture and Sports (USA) [1]. It shows that immediately after the magazine was released in January 1924, called "Physical Fitness" (this is the first use of the term "fitness" in the title of the official publication), its publishers were forced to change the name to "Mental, Physical and Moral Fitness" in order to avoid, as stated in the report, prosecution by B. McFadden. In January 1925, this magazine ceased to exist. Note that at that time the use of the terms "physical fitness" and "fitness" to characterize the results of physical activity was not accidental. So, Catharine Beecher (Catharine Beecher) in 1832 used the term "fitness" to substantiate the need for the introduction of exercise in US schools. This term was actively used at the beginning of the 20th century and in England in the process of improving physical education in public schools, to assess the compliance of physical fitness of schoolchildren [10]. To this, it should also be added that during the indicated period the word "fitness" was widely used in natural sciences. For example, it is found in the work by L. Joseph Henderson "Fitness of the Environment" (1913) to characterize that the environment corresponds to the conditions of life development [11], as well as in biology to characterize the quantitative measure of natural selection (Darwinian fitness) [12].

Conclusions / Discussion

The analysis performed allows us to make the following generalization. Based on the selected mechanism of self-development of social phenomena, which is based on the law "the interrelation of needs and activities" [5], it is necessary to recognize that the driving forces that determine the self-development of physical fitness as a socially significant phenomenon, manifested in the dialectical unity, on the one hand, business -interests of the organizers of such activities, and on the other hand, the need in a similar type of activity existing in society. The situation is formulated is confirmed by the following historical facts, indicating that already in the 19th century in a large number of countries in Europe, in the UK and in the USA, a significant number of various venues, halls, studios, salons in which people exercised were functioning. For example, in Germany, the first gymnastics grounds (Turnplatz) were opened by F. Jan in Berlin in 1811. In Paris, the famous Hippolyte Triat athlete founded in 1847 several gymnasts for bourgeois, aristocrats and energetic young people, and Professor E. Desbonnet at the turn of the 20th century had around 300 similar institutions throughout France and Europe. In the US, the first such room in 1824 was discovered by C. Beck. The same work was carried out by D. A. Sargent, who at the end of the 19th century organized several rooms at Harvard University, as well as B. McFadden, who founded his first studio in 1875, calling it "Bernard McFadden – a teacher of Higher Physical Culture". In the United Kingdom in 1858, S. A. MacLaren opened a similar hall at Oxford University, and E. Sandov created in London at the end of the 19th century a whole network of similar "institutions", which at that time were called the institutes of physical culture. All these "halls", "studios", "institutions", "salons" were designed for different layers of population, from modest establishments for representatives of the middle class to many arranged salons for aristocrats. Historical materials indicate that such organizations, for example, B. McFadden (USA), E. Desbonnet (France) and especially E. Sandov (Great Britain), earned large profits on the organization. A significant factor that influenced the development of such activity was its informational support. Historical materials indicate that in the UK E. Sandov issued from 1898 to 1907 Sandov Journal of Physical Education magazine (the first name of the journal Physical Education). In the US, the same work on advertising the activities of people related to the use of physical exercises was carried out by B. McFadden, who created an entire publishing empire, which was based on the journal Physical Education. created together with the writer A. Surier magazine "Physical Education".

Thus, based on the results of the above analysis, and also taking into account the results of D. McFadden's (USA), D. Lewis (USA), E. Sandova (UK) and E. Dasbonneet (France) as outstanding historians, a significant contribution to the development of physical culture, we can conclude that at the turn of the 20th century the term "physical culture" was used as a generalization of the three directions of human activity associated with the use of physical exercises: first, activities aimed at bringing (physical fitness), secondly, activities aimed at the development of physical strength and body composition (bodybuilding); thirdly, activities aimed at improving with the use of physical exercises (therapeutic physical culture).

Secondly, within the framework of the theory of physical culture, physical fitness is considered as a special socio-cultural phenomenon, which is a historically conditioned activity of people associated with the use of physical exercise at leisure, as well as individual and socially significant results of such activity.

Conflict of interests. The authors declare that no conflict of interest.
Financing sources. This article didn't get the financial support from the state, public or commercial organization.

References

1. Annotated bibliography of serial editions in English in the field of physical culture (from 1829 to 1990 year inclusive), available at: <http://library.la84.org/SportsLibrary/IGH/IGH0104/IGH0104k.pdf>
2. Vasil Sutula (2018), "Problems and Perspectives of Construction of the Generalized Theory of Physical Culture", *Journal of Physical Fitness, Medicine & Treatment in Sport*, Vol. 3 (4), pp. 01-02, available at: <https://juniperpublishers.com/jpfmts/pdf/JPFMTS.MS.ID.555620.pdf>.
3. Sutula, V.O. (2016), "Physical Culture: The Preconditions of Theory", *Teoriia i metodyka fizychnoho vykhovannia i sportu*, No. 3, pp. 60-65. (in Ukr.)
4. Vasil Sutula (2018), "Generalizing the definition of" sport "as one of the basic constructs of generalizing the theory of physical culture and the theory of sport", *Slobozans'kiy naukovo-sportivnyy visnik*, No. 1(63), pp. 89-97, doi: 10.15391/snsv.2018-1.016. (in Ukr.)
5. Vasil Sutula (2017), "Conceptual Provisions of the Generalized Theory of Physical Culture", *Teoriia i metodyka fizychnoho vykhovannia i sportu*, No. 3, pp. 107-115. (in Ukr.)
6. Vasil Sutula (2016), "The essence of the connection between physical culture, physical recreation and physical fitness", *Teoriia i metodyka fizychnoho vykhovannia i sportu*, No. 4, pp. 77-84. (in Ukr.)
7. Glassman, G. (2002), "What Is Fitness and Who Is Fit?", available at: <https://crossfithreshold.wordpress.com/what-is-fitness-and-who-is-fit/>.
8. Le Corre, E. (2014), "The History of Physical Fitness", available at: <http://www.artofmanliness.com/2014/09/24/the-history-of-physical-fitness/>
9. Sifferman, J. (2009), "Physical Culture: it's more than just bodybuilding, muscles, and old-time strongmen training culture", available at: <http://physicalliving.com/physical-culture-its-more-than-just-bodybuilding-muscles-and-old-time-strongmen-training-culture/>.
10. Kun, L. (1982), *Vseobshchaya istoriya fizicheskoy kultury* [The General History of Physical Education], Raduga, Moscow. (in Russ.)
11. Henderson, L.J. (1913), *The Fitness of the Environment An Inquiry Into the Biological Significance of the Properties of Matter*, available at: <http://www.geology.19thcenturyscience.org/books/1913HendersonFitness/htm/doc.html>
12. Encyclopxdia Britannica (2018), Darwinian fitness, available at: <https://www.britannica.com/science/Darwinian-fitness>

Received: 19.07.2018.

Published: 31.08.2018.

Information about the Authors

Vasyl Sutula: Doctor of Science (Pedagogical), Professor; Kharkiv State Academy of Physical Culture: Klochkovskaya 99, Kharkiv, 61058, Ukraine.

ORCID.ORG/0000-0002-1108-9640

E-mail: vsutula@rambler.ru

Larysa Lutsenko: PhD (Physical Education and Sport), Associat Professor; Law University named after Yaroslav the Wise: Pushkinskaya Str. 77, Kharkiv, 61024, Ukraine.

ORSID.ORG/0000-0001-6459-8564

E-mail: l.s.lutsenkospport@gmail.com

Andrey Zhadan: PhD (Physical Education and Sport); Kharkiv State Academy of Physical Culture: Klochkivska 99, Kharkiv, 61058, Ukraine.

ORCID.ORG/0000-0002-2718-6373

E-mail: doctorandrey.www@gmail.com

Anastasiia Sutula: National Pharmaceutical University: st. Pushkinskaya, 53, Kharkiv, 61000, Ukraine.

ORCID.ORG/0000-0001-6459-8564

E-mail: nastja.sutula@rambler.ru